

WORK-RELATED STRESSORS AND JOB PERFORMANCE OF SECONDARY TEACHERS: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED TRAINING PROGRAM

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Work-Related Stressors and Job Performance of Secondary Teachers: Basis for a Proposed Training Program

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the extent of work-related stressors of secondary teachers and its relationship to their job performance in secondary schools of Pasig City during the school year 2023-2024 to serve as a basis for a proposed training program. The design used in this study was descriptive correlational with the survey questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument. The weighted mean, t-test and Pearson r were the statistical tools used to treat the data. The respondents were composed of 236 teachers and five school heads in public secondary schools in District II, Division of Pasig City. Based on the findings, the teacher's extent of experience with work-related stressors based on the three key indicators (i.e. workload, students' behavior, and responsiveness to stakeholders), was moderate with a grand weighted mean of 1.58. In addition, Both the teachers and the school heads strongly agree with the indicators that describe the level of teacher's performance in terms of classroom management, lesson planning, lesson delivery and assessment of learning. Likewise, there was no significant relationship between the work-related stressors experienced by the teachers and their level of performance. Furthermore, stress prevention and management were deemed necessary, thus, was proposed in this study.

Keywords: *work-related stressors, job performance, training program*

Introduction

In the educational landscape, teachers play an indispensable role as the cornerstone of student learning and academic development (Raj, 2023). Their influence extends far beyond the classroom, shaping not only academic outcomes but also the socio-emotional growth of their students (Valiente et al., 2020). However, amidst the noble pursuit of cultivating young minds, teachers often contend with an array of stressors that can significantly impact their job performance and overall well-being (Cahilog et al., 2023).

The modern educational environment presents myriad challenges for teachers, ranging from increasing administrative demands to diverse student needs and societal pressures (Popov et al., 2021). These stressors, if left unaddressed, can lead to burnout, decreased job satisfaction, and ultimately, hindered effectiveness in the classroom (Agyapong et al., 2022).

Similar to this global counterparts, Filipino teachers encounter a multitude of stressors in their professional lives, stemming from various sources such as heavy workloads, limited resources, and complex administrative requirements (Tarraya, 2023). Additionally, societal expectations and cultural norms place additional pressure on educators to deliver exceptional outcomes despite often constrained circumstances (Damşa et al., 2021).

Despite the resilience and dedication exhibited by Filipino teachers and the reinforcement policies on teacher's welfare of DepEd, the impact of stressors on their job performance and well-being cannot be ignored (Go et al., 2020). Burnout, decreased job satisfaction, and diminished effectiveness in the classroom are all too common consequences of unaddressed work-related stressors (Hossain & Sultana, 2022) especially among the teachers in the District II within the Division of Pasig City. According to the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) data presented by the Division office of Pasig City, there is a decrease in the performance level of teachers in the elementary and secondary level during the school year 2019 to 2023. This can be attributed to the work-related stressors in the following areas: constant workload, the management of student behavior, and communication/responsiveness to internal stakeholders. These stressors could also impact their performance in critical aspects of teaching, such as classroom management, lesson planning, delivery, and assessment of learning.

The critical importance of supporting educators in navigating these challenges is paramount to ensuring the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4: Quality Education. SDG 4 which emphasizes the importance of ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education for all, which is only attainable when educators are adequately supported and empowered to fulfill their roles effectively. Therefore, this study aligns with the broader global agenda of advancing education quality and promoting the well-being of educators as integral components of sustainable development.

In the light of the foregoing facts, the researcher thought of a study on the specific work-related stressors prevalent in District II by delving into the intricacies of teacher stressors and their effects on job performance. In this context, this study aims to provide empirical insights that will serve as the foundation for the development of needed training programs.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the work-related stressors experienced by the teachers and its relationship to their job performance in public secondary schools of District II, Division of Pasig city. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent do the teacher respondents experience work-related stressors in terms of the following variables:
 - 1.1. workload;
 - 1.2. student behavior; and
 - 1.3. responsiveness to stakeholders?
2. What is the level of job performance of the teacher-respondents as assessed by the teachers themselves in terms of the following aspects:
 - 2.1. classroom management;
 - 2.2. lesson planning;
 - 2.3. lesson delivery; and
 - 2.4. assessment of learning?
3. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the teacher's level of job performance in terms of aforementioned aspects?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the work-related stressors experienced by the teacher respondents and their level of job performance?
5. What stress prevention and management program may be proposed based on the result of the study

Literature Review

According to Asaloei et al. (2020), it is natural for educators to have multitude of work-related stressors that significantly impact their job performance and overall well-being because of the importance of their professions in shaping the society. One prevalent stressor highlighted across studies is the constant workload teachers contend with on a daily basis (Carroll et al., 2022). This relentless demand for planning lessons, grading assignments, and attending to administrative tasks can lead to feelings of overwhelm and exhaustion, ultimately affecting their ability to deliver quality instruction (Gonzalez, 2021). The burden of workload stands as a formidable stressor that permeates every aspect of a teacher's professional life (Geronimo & Campoamor-Olegario, 2020).

Moreover, the pervasive nature of workload stressors extends beyond the classroom, impacting teachers' mental and emotional well-being (Jain, 2021). On the other hand, Ang (2023), highlighted that burnout among educators is attributed in part to the perpetual demands of their profession. The incessant pressure to meet deadlines, fulfill administrative obligations, and cater to the diverse needs of students can lead to feelings of exhaustion, frustration, and disillusionment. Consequently, workload stressors not only affect teachers' job satisfaction but also their overall effectiveness in the classroom (Toropova et al., 2020).

In delving into the intricacies of classroom management, lesson planning, delivery, and assessment, it becomes evident that these facets of job performance are inextricably linked, constituting the scaffolding upon which effective teaching rests (Franklin & Harrington, 2019). Despite the manifold stressors that educators grapple with, prioritizing these elements can yield tangible benefits for both teachers and students (Will et al., 2023). By investing in professional development opportunities tailored to enhance pedagogical skills, providing robust support structures, and cultivating a culture of collaboration and reflective practice, educational institutions can empower teachers to navigate the complexities of their profession with confidence and proficiency (Smeplass, 2023). Ultimately, the optimization of these foundational pillars fosters an educational milieu characterized by engagement, efficacy, and equitable academic outcomes for all students (Steele et al., 2023).

Bongco and Ancho (2019) examined the professional workload of Filipino teachers, highlighting the diverse range of responsibilities, including classroom teaching and administrative duties that contribute to stress levels among educators. Research in the Philippines indicate that what teacher does in the classroom significantly influence learning and one of which is classroom management (Llego 2022). Similarly, Jain's (2021) study on primary school teachers in New Zealand revealed the prevalence of work stress, driven by factors such as heavy workload and student behavior issues.

Sarabia and Collantes (2020) study entitled "Work-related Stress and Teaching Performance of Teachers in Selected School in the Philippines" also agreed that work-related stress was moderate, mainly due to high demand, while factors like control, change, role, support, and coworker relationships had less impact.

Similarly, Agyapong et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of implementing school-based interventions universally to enhance teachers' stress-coping abilities and prevent burnout. Despite challenges such as time constraints, they argued that prioritizing suitable interventions tailored to reduce stress and burnout among teachers is crucial, even amidst busy schedules.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized quantitative research method specifically using descriptive-correlational design. Quantitative method involves the collection of numerical data to quantify phenomena and analyze relationships between variables (Sreekumar, 2023). In the context of this study, this method involves structured surveys or questionnaires administered to teacher-respondents and school heads to gather data on work-related stressors and job performance.

Descriptive approach involves describing the characteristics of a phenomenon or group without seeking to establish relationships or causality (Sirisilla, 2023). In

Finally, correlational approach involves examining the relationship between two or more variables to determine if changes in one variable correspond with changes in another (Bhandari, 2023).

Respondents

The study employed simple random sampling utilizing Slovin's formula to select teacher respondents. This technique was chosen to ensure that every teacher in the population of District II in the Division of Pasig City has an equal chance of being selected resulting to a total of 236 secondary teacher.

In terms of determining the number of school heads, the study utilized a "census survey" sampling method. This involved including all school heads the five secondary schools of District II Division of Pasig City as respondents. This results to a total of five secondary school heads.

Instrument

The researcher employed a researcher-made questionnaire as an instrument in gathering data from the respondents. The researcher conducted an extensive reading about the variables for the development of the questionnaire. In addition, the researcher used the internet to collect relevant ideas, concepts, and information from related theories and literature related to the study that served as the basis of the questionnaire.

The second set of instruments was designed for the school heads, and it consisted of questions about the level of job performance of teachers in terms of classroom management, lesson planning, lesson delivery and assessment of learning.

Procedure

The needed data in this study were collected following gathering procedures: The gathering of data started by writing and sending a letter to the school heads of the public secondary schools in District II of the Division of Pasig City, asking permission for the conduct of the study and discussing the researchers' intention to have the teachers and them as the respondents. After approval, the researcher sent a letter of intent to the respondents. The school heads and teachers have the right to make their own decisions about whether or not to participate in the study. This means that participation should be voluntary, and participants are free to withdraw at any time without facing any negative consequences.

Questionnaires were scheduled for distribution and were collected through online platforms, specifically Google Forms, the researcher took steps to ensure the security of the data. This included using secure data transmission methods, such as encryption, and implementing measures to prevent unauthorized access to the data.

The researcher interpreted the responses after they were examined, categorized, assessed, tabulated, and evaluated with the use of statistical tools. The researcher gave assurance to the teacher-respondents that their answers would be held with strict confidentiality and only used for research purposes only.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher observed the necessary ethics in the conduct of her study. She first informed the respondents regarding their involvement in the study and got their consent. She also explained to the respondents that their participation was voluntary and their responses to the questionnaire would be treated with utmost confidentiality and anonymity.

Results and Discussion

Teacher Respondent's Extent of Experience of Work-Related Stressors

Table 1. *Teachers' Extent of Experience of Work-Related Stressors in terms of Workload*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Constant planning and preparation of lessons in limited time.	1.59	ME
2.	Grading assignments and exams that are become overwhelming.	1.63	ME
3.	Handling administrative duties, such as paperwork and documentation.	1.57	ME
4.	Participating in numerous meetings and committees.	1.55	ME
5.	Implementing a new curriculum or educational approach.	1.61	ME
6.	Handling large class sizes that require more effort and attention	1.64	ME
7.	Insufficient teaching materials and resources in making effective lesson planning.	1.58	ME
8.	Meeting continuous professional development goals	1.73	ME
9.	Unrealistic expectations from school administrators or parents.	1.50	ME
10.	Involvement in extra-curricular activities or supervising events outside regular teaching hours.	1.52	ME
	Average Weighted Mean	1.59	ME

Overall, the general weighted mean for workload-related stressors was 1.59 with the corresponding verbal interpretation moderate extent of stress. These findings underscore the diverse challenges teachers encounter in managing their workload, highlighting the importance of providing adequate support and resources to address these stressors effectively. Additionally, understanding the specific stressors teachers face could serve as basis for the development of targeted interventions aimed at promoting teacher's well-being and enhancing their job performance.

Asaloei et al. (2020) and Carroll et al. (2022) have highlighted the demanding nature of constant lesson planning, overwhelming grading tasks, and time-consuming administrative duties as significant stressors for teachers. According to them, these stressors are further compounded by factors such as participating in numerous meetings and committees, implementing new curriculum or educational approaches handling large class sizes and facing insufficient teaching materials and resources for effective lesson.

Table 2. Teachers' Extent of Experience of Work-Related Stressors in terms of Student Behavior

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Managing disruptive behavior and maintaining a positive classroom environment.	1.51	0.501	ME
2. Addressing the diverse learning needs of students.	1.47	0.500	LE
3. Dealing with bullying incidents and conflicts among students.	1.49	0.501	LE
4. Students showing a lack of motivation, making it challenging to engage them in the learning process.	1.51	0.501	ME
5. Catering to the unique needs of students with special education requirements.	1.61	0.605	ME
6. Disciplining troubled students.	1.58	0.604	ME
7. Communicating effectively with students who have language barriers.	1.61	0.605	ME
8. Managing a diverse range of students with different abilities and backgrounds.	1.61	0.640	ME
9. Dealing with the challenges of integrating technology into the classroom and managing student's distractions.	1.56	0.613	ME
10. Dealing with challenges related to assigning, collecting, and grading homework.	1.64	0.659	ME
Average Weighted Mean	1.56	0.578	ME

Overall, student behavior-related stressors were perceived to be at a moderate extent among teachers in public secondary schools of District II, Division of Pasig City. The findings indicate that teachers encounter a range of stressors related to managing student behavior, with notable concerns surrounding homework-related challenges.

Authors such as Kollerová et al. (2023) and Agyapong et al. (2022) have highlighted the challenges teachers face in managing disruptive behavior, motivating students, and addressing diverse learning needs.

Table 3. Teachers' Extent of Experience of Work-Related Stressors in terms of Responsiveness to Stakeholders

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Ensuring effective communication with parents, administrators, and colleagues	1.64	0.646	ME
2. Managing and meeting the expectations of parents.	1.64	0.628	ME
3. Accountability for student performance on standardized tests or other assessments.	1.60	0.634	ME
4. Insufficient support from school administration or colleagues	1.56	0.591	ME
5. Meeting professional development expectations imposed by stakeholders.	1.58	0.651	ME
6. Coordinating and collaborating on projects with other teachers and stakeholders.	1.57	0.665	ME
7. Preparing for and conducting parent-teacher conferences.	1.58	0.589	ME
8. Dealing with complaints or concerns from parents or stakeholders.	1.56	0.626	ME
9. Adhering to and implementing school policies.	1.59	0.629	ME
10. Juggling the expectations of parents, administrators, and community members.	1.64	0.666	ME
Average Weighted Mean	1.60	0.633	ME

Overall, responsiveness to stakeholders-related stressors was perceived to be at a moderate extent among teachers in public secondary schools of District II, Division of Pasig City.

The findings reveal that teachers face a range of stressors related to responsiveness to stakeholders, including communication challenges, meeting expectations, and dealing with complaints or concerns.

Daniel et al. (2023) and UNESCO-IIEP (2022) have emphasized the challenges teachers face in balancing the expectations of various stakeholders while maintaining effective communication and adhering to school policies.

Teachers' Level of Job Performance

The general weighted mean for classroom management, as assessed by both teachers and school heads, indicates a strong agreement regarding teachers' performance in this aspect. The data reveals that both teachers and school heads perceive teachers' performance in classroom management positively, with strong agreement indicated by high mean scores.

These findings align with the theoretical framework proposed by Bandura (1986), that emphasized that the teacher's high level of job performance in classroom management, as perceived by both teachers and school heads, reflects their confidence in effectively executing their tasks and fostering a conducive learning environment.

Table 4. *Teachers' Level of Job Performance in terms of Classroom Management*

Indicators	Teachers		School Heads	
	Weighted Mean	VI	Weighted Mean	VI
1. Teachers effectively maintain a positive and inclusive classroom environment.	3.59	VH	4.00	VH
2. Teachers' communication of classroom rules and expectations is clear, and they consistently enforce them.	3.49	H	4.00	VH
3. Teachers manage disruptions and behavior issues promptly and effectively.	3.58	VH	3.40	H
4. Transitions between activities are smooth and well-managed in teachers' classrooms.	3.81	VH	4.00	VH
5. Teachers foster a respectful and collaborative atmosphere among their students.	3.64	VH	3.60	VH
6. Teachers' classroom resources and materials are organized and readily accessible.	3.58	VH	3.40	H
7. Teachers employ a variety of strategies to engage and motivate students in the learning process.	3.33	H	3.40	H
8. Teachers handle diverse student needs and learning styles effectively in their classrooms.	3.52	VH	3.80	VH
9. Teachers utilize time efficiently, and their instructional activities are well-paced.	3.58	VH	3.60	VH
10. Teachers demonstrate adaptability in addressing unexpected challenges related to classroom management.	3.69	VH	3.80	VH
Average Weighted Mean	3.58	VH	3.70	VH

The general weighted mean for lesson planning, as assessed by both teachers and school heads, indicates a positive perception of teachers' performance in this aspect, although slightly higher among teachers. The analysis reveals a positive perception of teachers' performance in lesson planning, with both teachers and school heads generally agreeing on the effectiveness of teachers in this aspect.

Table 5. *Teachers' Level of Job Performance in terms of Lesson Planning*

Indicators	Teachers		School Heads	
	Weighted Mean	VI	Weighted Mean	VI
1. Teachers' lesson plans are well-organized and clearly outline learning objectives.	3.69	VH	3.80	VH
2. Teachers incorporate appropriate and varied instructional strategies in their lesson plans.	3.52	VH	3.40	H
3. Teachers consider differentiated instruction to meet diverse student needs in lesson planning.	3.53	VH	3.20	H
4. Teachers' lesson plans align with curriculum standards and educational objectives.	3.74	VH	3.60	VH
5. Teachers consider students' prior knowledge and experiences in their lesson plans.	3.69	VH	3.40	H
6. Teachers effectively integrate technology and resources into their lesson plans.	3.56	VH	3.60	VH
7. Teachers' lesson plans include assessments that align with learning objectives.	3.42	H	3.00	H
8. Teachers provide opportunities for student engagement and participation in their lesson plans.	3.62	VH	3.60	VH
9. Teachers' lesson plans are flexible and allow for adjustments based on student needs.	3.59	VH	3.20	H
10. Teachers demonstrate creativity and innovation in developing their lesson plans.	3.72	VH	3.40	H
General Weighted Mean	3.61	VH	3.42	H

According to Asaloei et al. (2020), educators experience significant work-related stressors due to the demanding nature of their profession, including workload stressors such as lesson planning.

Table 6. *Teachers' Level of Job Performance in terms of Lesson Delivery*

Indicators	Teachers		School Heads	
	Weighted Mean	VI	Weighted Mean	VI
1. Teachers effectively communicate lesson content in a clear and engaging manner.	3.59	VH	3.40	H
2. Instructional methods used by teachers promote active student participation.	3.46	H	3.20	H
3. Teachers use a variety of multimedia and visual aids to enhance lesson delivery.	3.53	VH	3.20	H
4. Teachers convey enthusiasm and passion for the subject matter during lesson delivery.	3.68	VH	3.60	VH
5. Teachers manage time effectively during lesson delivery to cover planned	3.67	VH	3.60	VH

6.	Teachers address student questions with clarity and encouragement during lessons.	3.53	VH	3.20	H
7.	Teachers create a positive and inclusive learning atmosphere during lesson delivery.	3.44	H	3.60	VH
8.	Differentiated instruction is evident in teachers' approaches to lesson delivery.	3.55	VH	4.00	VH
9.	Teachers adapt lesson delivery based on formative assessment and student feedback.	3.53	VH	4.00	VH
10.	Instructional activities are well-paced, allowing for student understanding and engagement.	3.60	VH	3.60	VH
Average Weighted Mean		3.56	VH	3.54	VH

The general weighted mean for lesson delivery, as assessed by both teachers and school heads, indicates a positive perception of teachers' performance in this aspect, with both groups strongly agreeing on the High-level performance of teachers in various dimensions of lesson delivery.

As highlighted by Carroll et al. (2022) and Varthana (2024), the demanding nature of lesson delivery tasks, including effective communication of lesson content and time management, can contribute to feelings of overwhelm and exhaustion among teachers.

Table 7. Teachers' Level of Job Performance in terms of Assessment of Learning

Indicators	Teachers		School Heads		
	Weighted Mean	VI	Weighted Mean	VI	
1. Teachers' assessments are aligned with the stated learning objectives.	3.62	VH	3.20	H	
2. Teachers use a variety of assessment methods to gauge student understanding.	3.56	VH	3.60	VH	
3. Assessments designed by teachers are fair and unbiased, accommodating diverse student needs.	3.62	VH	3.60	VH	
4. Feedback provided by teachers on assessments is constructive and meaningful.	3.61	VH	3.60	VH	
5. Teachers use formative assessments to guide instructional decisions.	3.56	VH	3.40	H	
6. Assessment results are used by teachers to identify areas for instructional improvement.	3.56	VH	3.40	H	
7. Teachers effectively communicate assessment expectations to their students.	3.44	H	3.00	H	
8. Students are provided with opportunities for self-assessment and reflection in teachers' classes.	3.52	VH	3.00	H	
9. Teachers use assessment data to differentiate instruction for individual students.	3.57	VH	3.20	H	
10. Teachers' assessment practices encourage a positive and growth-oriented mindset among students.	3.67	VH	3.60	VH	
Average Weighted Mean		3.57	VH	3.36	H

The general weighted mean for assessment of learning, as assessed by both teachers and school heads, indicates a positive perception of teachers' performance in this aspect, although slightly higher among teachers. Teachers are perceived to effectively align assessments with learning objectives, use a variety of assessment methods, and provide constructive feedback to students.

As discussed by White Olivier (2021) and Wanner & Palmer (2019), effective assessment practices play a crucial role in gauging student understanding and guiding instructional decisions.

Significant Difference in the Assessment of Teachers and School Heads on the Teacher's Level of Job Performance

Table 8. Mann-Whitney U Test of Difference between the Assessments of Teachers and School Heads on the Teacher's Level of Job Performance

	Teacher's Level of Job Performance			
	Classroom Management	Lesson Planning	Lesson Delivery	Assessment of Learning
Mann-Whitney U	389	324.5	575	294
Wilcoxon W	28355	339.5	28541	309
Z	-1.317	-1.737	-0.098	-1.935
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.188	0.082	0.922	0.053

This suggests a high level of agreement between teachers and school heads regarding teachers' performance in these areas. It underscores the importance of mutual understanding and collaboration between teachers and school leadership in evaluating and improving teacher effectiveness. Asaloei et al. (2020) highlighted the significant impact of workload stressors on teachers' job performance and overall well-being. This supports the idea that both teachers and school heads may perceive similar challenges related

to workload management, leading to a convergence in their assessment of teachers' performance in domains such as Classroom Management and Lesson Planning.

Table 9. *Test of Relationship between the Work-Related Stressors Experienced by Teachers and their Level of Job Performance*

Work-Related Stressors	Level of Job Performance			
	Classroom Management	Lesson Planning	Lesson Delivery	Assessment of Learning
Workload	-0.037	0.051	0.082	-0.022
Student Behavior	-0.061	0.036	0.05	-0.006
Responsiveness to Stakeholders	-0.051	-0.005	0.003	0.03

In conclusion, the analysis of the correlation table indicates that there was no significant relationship between the work-related stressors experienced by teachers and their level of job performance. This suggests that while teachers may experience various stressors in their work environment, these stressors do not have a substantial impact on their job performance in the evaluated domains.

Carroll et al. (2022) emphasized the impact of workload demands on teachers' stress levels and overall well-being. However, the weak and non-significant correlations observed between workload and job performance in the table align with the idea that while workload stressors may exist, they do not necessarily translate into measurable effects on job performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

The teacher respondents encounter work-related stressors in their respective schools.

The teacher respondents perform well their teaching job despite of experiencing some work-related stressors.

Both the school head and the teachers in the school share similar views on the teacher's level of job performance.

The work-related stressors experienced by the teacher respondents have no bearing on their level of job performance.

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